

First report of palea browning in China and characterization of the causal organism by phenotypic tests and Biolog

Xie Guanlin, Institute of Biocontrol of Plant Diseases, Zhejiang University, 268 Kaixuan Road, Hangzhou 310029, China
E-mail: glxie@zju.edu.cn

In recent years, a bacterial disease of rice was observed in the field in Jiangxi and Yuhang, Zhejiang Province, China. The disease usually occurs at early flowering of late rice (japonica varieties). Initially, light, rusty, water-soaked lesions appear on the lemma or palea. The lesions then turn brown. The discoloration occurs most frequently on the palea. More immature and lighter grains are observed on panicles at harvest. The disease was reported in Japan, Korea, and the Philippines but not previously in China (Azegami et al 1983, Kim et al 1989, Xie 1996). Therefore, the author determined the causal organism and compared it with *Pantoea agglomerans* (formerly *Erwinia herbicola*) (Gavini et al 1989), the causal organism of palea browning in rice from Japan.

Three and seven seed samples of rice (4–5 g sample⁻¹) with palea browning were collected from Jiangxi and Yuhang, respectively, in 1998–99. Isolations were done by plating serial dilution of seed washes (10⁻³–10⁻⁵ g⁻¹) on nutrient agar medium. Colony morphology was described and phenotypic and pathogenicity tests followed (Mew and Misra 1994, Azegami et al 1983, Xie 1996). Four standard reference strains (*Erwinia herbicola* J301742, *E. herbicola* J301752, *E. ananas* J301714, and *E. ananas* J301722) were provided by the National Institute of Agrobiological Resources, Japan. Additionally, Biolog (Biolog Inc., Investment Blvd. 3447, Suite 3, Hayward, Calif. 94545, USA) with software version 3.5 was used to further characterize the isolates.

Twelve bacterial isolates from 10 rice samples with palea browning showed characteristics similar to those of the reference strains of *P. agglomerans* in the phenotypic, pathogenicity, and Biolog

tests. The bacterium was Gram-negative and facultative fermentative. It had 2–6 peritrichous flagella, and it produced a

yellow water-soluble pigment. Table 1 shows 39 phenotypic characteristics of the isolates similar to those of *P. agglomerans*

Table 1. Phenotypic characterization of 12 isolates isolated from rice grains showing palea browning collected from Jiangxi and Yuhang of Zhejiang Province, China.

Phenotypic test	Isolates tested		Reference strains ^a	
	6 (Jiangxi) ^b	6 (Yuhang) ^c	<i>P. agglomerans</i> (J301742 and J301752)	<i>P. ananas</i> (J301714 and J301722)
Gram staining	–	–	–	–
Flagellation	+	+	+	+
O-F test ^d	+	+	+	+
Yellow pigment	+	+	+	+
Fluorescent pigment	–	–	–	–
Pink diffusible pigment	–	–	–	–
Growth factors required	–	–	–	–
Growth at 40 °C	+	+	+	+
H ₂ S from cysteine	+	+	+	–
Reducing sugar	–	v	–	+
Indole test	+	+	+	+
Gelatin liquefaction	+	+	+	+
Acetoin	+	+	+	+
Nitrate reduction	–	v	–	–
Urease	–	–	–	–
Phenylalanine deaminase	v	–	–	–
DNase	–	–	–	–
Lecithinase	–	–	–	–
Gas from glucose	–	–	–	–
Casein hydrolysis	–	–	–	–
Cotton seed oil hydrolysis	–	–	–	–
Growth in 5% NaCl	+	+	+	+
Acid production from				
Melibiose	+	v	+	+
Arabinose	+	+	+	+
Mannitol	+	+	+	+
Salicin	v	+	+	+
Raffinose	v	+	+	+
Lactose	v	+	+	+
Maltose	+	+	+	+
Cellobiose	v	+	+	+
Dextrin	–	–	–	–
Glycerol	v	+	+	+
Mannose	+	+	+	+
Rhamnose	+	+	+	–
Ribose	+	+	+	+
Sorbitol	+	v	+	+
Sucrose	+	+	+	+
Trehalose	+	+	+	+
Starch	v	–	–	+
Isolates tested (no.)	6	6	2	2

^a+ = 83–100% isolates positive; v = 33–82% isolated variable, – = 83–100% isolates negative; four reference strains isolated from rice grains in Japan. ^bIsolated from rice grains in Jiangxi. ^cIsolated from rice grains in Yuhang. ^dOxidation-fermentation test.

reference strains. Production of H₂S from cysteine, reducing sugar, and production of acid from starch and rhamnose differentiated the 12 isolates from *Pantoea ananas* (*E. ananas*). Six isolates induced discoloration of palea when inoculated at flowering stage by spraying. The rate of discolored grains on a panicle was 2.1–12.6%, which varied based on isolate, age of the rice plant, and environmental conditions (mainly temperature and moisture) for inoculation (Azegami et al 1983). The six selected strains isolated from discolored grains were identified as *P. agglomerans* by Biolog, which confirmed the two reference strains as *P. agglomerans* with similarity indices of 0.611 and 0.930 (Table 2).

The causal organism of palea browning in Zhejiang Province has been phenotypically identified as *P.*

Table 2. Identity of causal bacterium of palea browning of rice by Biolog.

Code of isolate	Biolog identification	Similarity index
CB98301	<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	0.971
CB97311	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.930
CB98370	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.911
CB97303	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.894
CB97318	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.863
CB98369	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.827

agglomerans. It can be concluded that it is the same causal organism reported in Japan in 1983.

References

- Azegami K, Ozaki K, Matsuda A. 1983. Bacterial palea browning, a new disease of rice caused by *Erwinia herbicola*. Bull. Natl. Inst. Agric. Sci. Ser. C 39:1–12.
- Gavini F, Mergaert J, Beji A, Mielcarek C, Izard D, Kersters K, Ley J de. 1989. Transfer of *Enterobacter agglomerans* (Beijerinck 1888) Ewing and Fife 1972 to *Pantoea* gen. nov. as *Pantoea agglomerans* comb. nov. and description of *Pantoea dispersa* sp. nov. Int. J. Syst. Bacteriol. 39(3):337–345.
- Kim YC, Kim KC, Cho BH. 1989. Palea browning disease of rice caused by *Erwinia herbicola* and ice nucleation activity of the pathogenic bacteria. Korean J. Plant Pathol. 5(1):72–79.
- Mew TW, Misra JK. 1994. A manual of rice seed health testing. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 220 p.
- Xie GL. 1996. Characterization of *Pseudomonas* spp. and other bacterial species associated with rice seeds. PhD thesis, University of the Philippines Los Baños, Philippines. 170 p.

Expression of *Bt* genes under control of different promoters in rice at vegetative and flowering stages

R.M. Aguda, K. Datta, J. Tu, S.K. Datta, and M.B. Cohen, IRRI E-mail: m.cohen@cgiar.org

Toxin-encoding genes from the bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) have been widely used in plant transformation to confer resistance to insect pests. These genes have been placed under the control of various promoters. Some, such as the cauliflower mosaic virus (CaMV) 35S and rice actin promoters, are constitutive promoters, that is, they drive gene expression in most tissues at most stages of plant development. Other promoters are tissue-specific, such as the maize phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase (PEPC) promoter, which is active only in tissues that are photosynthetically active, and the maize tryptophan synthase alpha subunit promoter, which is active in pith. To achieve adequate and sustainable insect control with *Bt* genes, the associated promoter should provide strong gene expression in tissues attacked by target pests during all stages of plant development that are attacked by the pests (Cohen et al 2000). In some cases, it may

also be useful to avoid toxin gene expression in tissues not attacked by target pests, such as roots or grain.

In rice, the principal target pests for control by *Bt* genes are the yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), and leafhoppers such as *Marasmia patnalis* Guenée. Alinia et al (2000) found that a rice line transformed with *Bt cryIAb* toxin gene under control of the PEPC promoter was highly resistant to stem borers and leaf-feeding pests at the vegetative stage, but that toxin titer and insect resistance dropped substantially at the flowering stage. In this study, we examined the resistance at the vegetative and flowering stages of *cryIAb*-transformed rice lines with the CaMV, actin, and pith-specific promoters. These lines were previously found to be resistant to YSB at the vegetative stage (Datta et al 1998, Tu et al 1998).

Lines with the pith-specific and CaMV 35S promoter were in the background of variety CBII, and the line with the actin promoter was variety IR72. All lines were homozygous-positive for the *cryIAb* gene. Nontransgenic plants of CBII and IR72 were used as controls. Bioassays were conducted in petri dishes using cut stems for YSB and SSB and cut leaves for *M. patnalis*, with one stem or leaf per petri dish. Six first-instar stem borer larvae or second-instar *M. patnalis* larvae were placed in each petri dish, and the number of dead, live, and unrecovered larvae was recorded after 4 d. One stem and one leaf were tested from each of 75 plants of each *cryIAb* line at the vegetative stage. Another stem and leaf from 50 of these plants were tested at the booting stage, and another stem and leaf from 25 plants at the flowering stage. Three stems or leaves were tested from one CBII and IR72 control plant at each growth stage. Each petri dish